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Forest Bathing - an Attractive Form of Sylver Tourism

Lesné kúpanie – atraktívna forma lesoturistiky

Mikołaj Jalinik, Tomasz Pawłowicz

Forest areas are an environment to which society has been adapted for hundreds of thousands of years and which contains many components necessary for health, taking into account the migration of people to cities and urban agglomerations. The forest is a "factory" of oxygen, space, flora and fauna, bioaerosols, phytoncides and essential oils secreted by trees, which have beneficial effects on health and a sense of well-being. These ingredients have an extremely effective influence on the nervous system and forest therapy, which is beneficial in the fight against stress, hypertension and depression. Forest bathing as a part of sylvotherapy, tree therapy translates into the physical condition of the human body. The surrounding nature and its beauty are an opportunity to stop and experience the healing influence of nature on human health and has been known for centuries. The aim of the study is to present the importance of forest bathing as a form of sylver tourism and their healing properties. Specialist literature and inductive and deductive methods were used to prepare the study.

Key words: Forest bathing. Forest areas. Health. Sylver Tourism.

Lesné oblasti sú prostredím, ktorému bola spoločnosť prispôbovaná už státisíce rokov a ktoré obsahuje mnohé zložky potrebné pre zdravie s prihliadnutím na migráciu ľudí do miest a mestských aglomerácií. Les je „továreň“ kyslíka, vesmíru, flóry a fauny, bioaerosólov, fytoncídov a éterických olejov vylučovaných stromami, ktoré majú blahodarné účinky na zdravie a pocit pohody. Tieto zložky majú mimoriadny účinok na nervový systém a lesnú terapiu, čo je prospešné v boji proti stresu, hypertenzii a depresii. Lesné kúpanie ako súčasť lesoturistiky má vplyv na fyzický stavu ľudského organizmu. Okolité príroda a jej krásy sú príležitosťou zastaviť sa a zažiť liečivý vplyv prírody na ľudský organizmus, ktorý je známy už po stáročia. Cieľom štúdie je prezentovať význam lesného kúpania ako formy lesoturistiky a ich liečivé vlastnosti. Na vypracovanie štúdie bola použitá odborná literatúra a induktívne a deduktívne metódy.

Kľúčové slová: Lesné kúpanie. Lesné oblasti. Lesoturistika. Zdravie.

JEL Classification: I12, L83, Q23, Z32.

Introduction

Modern lifestyle, although it brings a lot of comfort, also causes a lot of stress. Every body needs regular exercise, and it is worth knowing that many diseases and ailments result from lack of physical activity. A slow walk among the trees lowers blood pressure and slows

down the heart rate, which has a calming effect on the body and the heart. The main advantage of systematic walks among trees is the reduction of cortisol and adrenaline levels, which are stress hormones. Every human tourist activity resulting from his needs and capabilities deserves recognition, because it is an extremely important component of a healthy lifestyle, which is so desirable nowadays (Stasiak and Włodarczyk, 2015).

More and more people are writing about forest bathing, which has been practiced in Japan for years. These are walks among stands of trees, which have been found to have extraordinary health-promoting properties in the form of relaxation and stress reduction. The concept of forest bathing comes from Japan and has been the subject of numerous scientific studies due to its potential health benefits. Many researchers agree that regular exposure to the forest environment can bring significant benefits to human physical and mental health (Twohig-Bennett and Jones, 2018).

When analyzing the presented issue, it is worth considering whether forest bathing is a tourist product. According to the marketing concept, a product is everything that meets the customer's needs and can be offered on the market. Therefore, the product may be material goods that usually complement other tourist products or can function independently (Kaczmarek, Stasiak, Włodarczyk, 2010). Forest air research was compared with urban air and it was proven that the forest climate has up to 70 times less pathogenic compounds and as much as 1,000 times less substances harmful to human health. Additionally, trees and shrubs regulate air ionization (Grzywacz, 2011).

A tourism product may be an area, facility, event, place, party, as well as services and others. In order to talk about a product, there must be a customer as a potential buyer who is willing and able to make a purchase and take advantage of the offer and bear the costs associated with it.

1. Sylver tourism - theoretical basis of research

Modern life makes society increasingly tired of the excess of various problems and information. Sylver tourism, although not appreciated until recently, is now gaining more and more recognition. Sylver tourism should be understood as short-term, organized collective or individual trips outside the place of permanent residence, wandering around a foreign forest area for sightseeing, entertainment, sports and relaxation purposes or as a form of active recreation, undertaken not for profit purposes (Mała encyklopedia leśna, 1991). Not only in the eyes of tourists, but also of people interested in spending their free time in an unpolluted

environment, such as forest areas. Tourism needs can be classified in many ways. They can also be assigned a specific hierarchy, e.g. like Maslow's pyramid of needs (Nogiec, 2011). Nowadays, consumers of tourism services express increasing expectations towards the tourism market. They expect that while staying in forest areas they will have access to the natural environment, which will make it easier for them to organize their holidays surrounded by forest stands. Tourists have noticed the potential of sylvan tourism, often referred to as forest bathing, as a result of which activities are being undertaken throughout the country to popularize tourist activity in the forest.

The practice of resting in forest areas was initiated in Japan in 1982 as part of a national health program aimed at reducing stress levels. Scientific research has proven that it is not enough to just be in the forest, but you have to enjoy its sights, sounds and smells. Since 2004, research has been regularly conducted in Japan on the impact of forest bathing on human physical and mental health.

Scientists have shown that trees have as many as 15 senses - 10 more than humans. They can communicate with each other, warn against enemies, and take care of each other during illness. They send electrical charges, ionizing the air, and secrete phytoncides and essential oils that have a health effect (Felber, 2020).

2. Aim, material and method

The aim of the study is to present the importance of forest bathing as a form of sylvan tourism and their impact on the health of society.

The study focused on available scientific literature foreign authors especially by Walker, Holling, Carpenter and Kinzig (2004), Li, Hser, Chen and Chang (2016) Hansen, Jones and Tocchini (2017), Twohig-Bennett and Jones (2018), Antonelli, Barbieri and Donelli (2019), Furuyashiki et al. (2019), Hurly and Walker (2019), Felber (2020), Stepansky, Delbert and Bucey (2022), McEwan, Krogh, K. S., Dunlop, Khan and Krogh, A. (2023), Subirana-Malaret, Miró, Camacho, Gesse and McEvan (2023) and domestic authors as Mała encyklopedia leśna (1991), Altkorn (2005), Mandziuk and Janeczko (2009), Kaczmarek, Stasiak and Włodarczyk (2010), Grzywacz (2011), Nogiec (2011), Stasiak and Włodarczyk (2015), Jalinik (2017, 2021) Jalinik and Bakier (2024), Grudzińska (2021). The authors used inductive and deductive methods.

3. Research results

3.1 Forest bathing as part of sylver tourism

Humanity has understood for thousands of years how contact with nature affects human well-being. Beautiful views, unpolluted environment, the smell of forest flora and peace have a soothing effect on everyone staying in the forest area. Forest bathing is a health-promoting practice of contact with nature, mainly the forest environment. Its essence is about slow, relaxing walks and experiencing the natural surroundings with all your senses. The idea of forest bathing is to "immerse" in the forest surroundings: climate, smells, humidity, aerobiological factors (phytoncides and essential oils) and forest bacterial flora. This means that forest bathing is used as a preventive, rehabilitation, relaxation and treatment supporting technique. Forest bathing traditions have deep roots in many cultures around the world. Although modern forest bathing practices in Japan, have gained popularity in recent decades in other countries - their roots go back to much earlier times (Li et al., 2016; Antonelli et al., 2019). In many traditional societies, the forest environment was considered a place of healing and spiritual renewal.

The term of forest bathing (*shinrin-yoku*) describes a procedure (like a bather immersing himself in water) was introduced in 1982 by Tomohide Akiyama (Grudzińska, 2021), whose idea was to combine a unique practice combining stays in the forest with health-promoting ecotourism. The concept of forest bathing was created in the 1980s, when the Japanese Forestry Agency began promoting the idea of forest walks to prevent and treat lifestyle diseases. Already in 1984, the American biologist E. O. Wilson began to popularize the theory of biophilia, the idea of people feeling the need to contact nature. He stated that contact with nature restores a sense of security, trust in the world, inner peace and joy of life (Sokołowska - accessed: August 28, 2023). Research conducted in Japan and China indicates that forest bathing can provide benefits in terms of lowering blood pressure, heart rate, and improving overall mental well-being (Hansen et al., 2017). Although the concept of forest bathing came from Japan as a widely used therapy, it also has its traditions in Europe and is deeply rooted in the culture of Scandinavian countries, Germany and Slavic countries. Since ancient times, people have owed their existence to forests and their wealth.

Slow walks in forest areas strengthen the body and normalize vital parameters such as blood pressure, heart rate, glycemia level and immune processes. In general, it can be said that it is an ideal, health-promoting form of spending free time in close contact with nature. For forest bathing to bring the most health benefits, you should follow a few rules and tips.

Walk in the forest or park should last about two hours. Forest bathing can be done alone or in a group, but it is important to refrain from and limit conversations. When going for a walk,

leave various amenities at home, e.g. telephone, newspapers, magazines. Forest bathing is characterized by a lack of rush, which is why stops and a journey without a destination are desirable. During the walk, you should focus on contemplating the beauty and fragments of nature. Time spent in the forest should be devoted to observing, listening, smelling and touching trees, leaves and moss. It is worth receiving them with all senses.

Research on *shinrin-yoku* and nature therapy highlights the need for further research in Western cultures to better understand the relationship between forest bathing, mindfulness, and well-being. Nevertheless, existing evidence suggests that combining these practices may offer an effective tool for promoting health and well-being in everyday life (Hansen et al., 2017).

Actively engaging with woodland spaces has significant benefits for physical, mental and social well-being. Depression, burnout and sleep disorders are now becoming common diseases. Studies have shown that regular exposure to the forest can reduce feelings of anxiety, isolation and stress levels. Additionally, spending free time in the forest can promote regeneration and rest from everyday stressors. In the context of a global trend, forest bathing is seen as an effective intervention to improve health and well-being, as well as to increase connection with nature (Stepansky et al., 2022).

3.2 Forest bathing resources as a tourist product

There are many definitions of a tourism product in the literature, which results from its diversity, complexity and service nature. In the simplest terms, a tourist product is the thing/things that a tourist buys, while in a broader sense, a tourist product is all the tourist's experiences from the moment the trip begins to the moment it ends, i.e. everything that tourists do during the trip, all the values, services, they use and the accompanying infrastructure (Mandziuk, Janeczko 2009). According to Altkorn (2005), a tourist product is a place in an accommodation facility, a sightseeing trip, a stay in a health resort, sightseeing (...) as well as the tourist attractions that exist in a given place. A tourist product is also a package of tangible and intangible components based on the opportunities to spend time in the destination. Such a package is perceived by the tourist as an experience available for a specific price.

The tourist product of forest areas is closely related to the form of tourism, which is sylvan tourism, which is one of the elements of nature tourism, which focuses on using forest areas as the main place for rest and recreation. Generally, it can be said that sylvan tourism is a form of tourism in forest areas and hence its close connection with forest bathing. Forest

areas, thanks to their unique tourist values, are becoming more and more popular among tourists seeking peace and experiences of closeness to nature (Jalinik, 2017). The tourist product of forest areas includes all tourist attractions occurring in a specific area. These are natural and cultural goods, in particular the natural and cultural values of forest areas (Jalinik, 2021). Natural values include: mature stands and their health properties, forest undergrowth products, elements enriching the forest landscape, unique flora and fauna, and forms of nature protection. The biotherapeutic properties of some species of forest trees and forest communities, e.g. pine forests or mixed forests, have long been known - they have a healing effect on respiratory diseases, have a disinfecting, bactericidal and fungicidal effect, and lower blood pressure. Birch forests have a similar effect, relieving depression, supporting the treatment of the urinary tract, strengthening the liver, lungs and hyperthyroidism (Jalinik, 2021).

Forest undergrowth products are very valuable, mainly in herbal medicine (phytotherapy), which is a permanent element of tradition, known since ancient times. Herbs found in unpolluted environments are a source of very valuable vitamins and digestible sugars. There are about 400 species of wild medicinal plants in Poland, and about 120 are forest species, including 50 species of trees and shrubs. Typical forest herbs constitute 15-20% of all herbs from natural sites. Blueberries, blackberries, raspberries, lingonberries, wild strawberries, cranberries and walnuts are also very often obtained (Mandziuk, Janeczko 2009).

Cultural values of forest areas, which are related to human activity and evidence of human existence in a given area, are also a tourist product. The most common values of this type include: historic forester's lodges, hunting lodges, forest souvenir chambers and forest technology chambers, museums, forest culture centers, educational training centers, excavations, cemeteries, places of martyrdom, war bunkers, and monuments. The forest is also a national heritage and a place of work for many artists, sculptors, painters, writers, poets and photographers.

Sylvan tourism products also include infrastructural elements of forest areas, personal service, market communication, education, as well as catering and accommodation facilities necessary to organize tourism and recreation in forest areas. The development of sylvan tourism as a specific form of nature tourism is a response to society's growing demand for direct contact with nature and for experiences related to authentic discovery of the world of plants and animals in their natural environment. Modern societies, living in a constant rush and dominated by technology, are increasingly looking for places that will allow them to

escape from everyday life and "immerse" themselves in the world of nature (Walker et al., 2004).

3.3 The therapeutic value of forest bathing

The first scientific experiment conducted in the Japanese city of Iiyama proved that forest bathing (Jalinik, Bakier, 2024): reduce stress and induce a state of natural relaxation; reduce anxiety, anger and depression; add energy and stimulate the immune system; improve the functioning of the respiratory, cardiovascular, digestive and hormonal systems; lower blood pressure and heart rate; extend sleep and improve its quality.

Modern research shows that forest bathing significantly affects the human psyche, bringing psychological and spiritual benefits. From a spiritual perspective, forest bathing allows the individual to have a deeper connection with nature, which can lead to a sense of oneness with the surrounding environment. For many people, it is an opportunity to reflect on man's place in the world and search for a deeper meaning in life (Hurly, Walker, 2019). In many cultures around the world, forests were and still are considered sacred places that have the power to heal and cleanse. Common practices include meditation, rituals and ceremonies performed in the forest to achieve spiritual enlightenment and physical health. Modern research confirms many traditional beliefs, pointing to numerous health benefits associated with staying in the forest, such as reducing stress levels, improving mood and strengthening the immune system (Antonelli et al., 2019).

The rapid development of technology, globalization and climate change do not remain indifferent to spa centers and the broadly understood wellness industry. The growing level of health awareness, the need to take care of one's physical condition, attractive appearance and well-being have been driving the dynamic development of the wellness industry for a long time. The centers are currently located in places far from civilization so that guests can have contact with wild nature and untouched by human activity. With the growing interest and focus on improving the quality of life and health, interest in therapies in forest areas is growing. That is why, every year, the number of countries and places surrounded by forests and pristine nature of wellness centers that specialize in forest treatment increases. Japan, Canada and the USA are leaders in the field of forest therapy due to their sustainable and multi-functional forest areas and rich wildlife. In Europe, this type of therapy is also becoming more and more popular, due to the ancient trees and spa and wellness traditions. Forest bathing is one of the latest trends in the wellness industry.

In recent years, they have become a global trend, responding to the growing demand of society. This mainly concerns the bond with nature and the use of its therapeutic benefits (Stepansky et al., 2022). International forest bathing research shows that experiencing nature can have significant health and well-being benefits. Study participants from various countries reported improved well-being after participating in forest bathing. The results suggest that experiencing nature, including the sounds, smells, peace and views of forests, and a favorable microclimate can bring significant benefits to mental and physical health (Subirana-Malaret et al., 2023).

First of all, trees and plants in the forest have a direct impact on well-being. This happens due to transmitter substances produced by trees - the so-called terpenes. Terpenes serve to protect the tree against pest invasion and are the main components of essential oils that have a stimulating or relaxing effect, strengthen the immune system, regulate blood pressure and relieve depression. During forest bathing, they are inhaled and absorbed through the mucous membranes of the respiratory tract, and in the body they in turn affect the immune system. Japanese research has shown that forest bathing also protects against cancer.

In a neurological context, forest bathing may act as a natural anti-anxiety and antidepressant (Table 1). Contact with nature can stimulate the nervous system to produce neurotransmitters that promote feelings of calm and relaxation. Therefore, forest bathing is often recommended as a natural adjunctive therapy for the treatment of mood and anxiety disorders.

Table 1 Changes in circulatory and autonomic functions due to bathing forests in healthy people and in people with depressive tendencies

		Wszystkie przypadki	Brak tendencji depresyjnej	Stwierdzona tendencja depresyjna	Wartość
Funkcje krążenia (%)	Liczba	155 (100%)	97 (62.6%)	58 (37.4%)	
SBP, mmHg	Przed	129.8 ± 20.4	130.2 ± 20.0	129.1 ± 21.1	0.632
	Po	121.5 ± 19.3	121.3 ± 19.0	121.9 ± 19.9	0.568
DBP, mmHg	Przed	79.0 ± 15.0	78.2 ± 15.4	80.2 ± 14.3	0.325
	Po	74.6 ± 13.8	73.5 ± 14.0	76.2 ± 13.0	0.250
PR, bpm	Przed	70.6 ± 11.0	70.7 ± 10.9	70.4 ± 11.3	0.685
	Po	71.1 ± 11.3	70.5 ± 11.6	72.1 ± 10.6	0.300
Funkcje autonomiczne (%)	Liczba	87 (100%)	48 (55.2%)	39 (44.8%)	
PR, bpm	Przed	68.25 ± 9.48	67.08 ± 9.81	69.68 ± 8.98	0.277
	Po	69.46 ± 10.44	67.68 ± 10.72	71.69 ± 9.76	0.034*
Aktywność parasympatykotoniczna	Przed	5.45 ± 1.13	5.50 ± 1.21	5.39 ± 1.05	0.788
	Po	5.36 ± 1.14	5.43 ± 1.03	5.28 ± 1.03	0.519
Aktywność sympatykotoniczna	Przed	1.03 ± 0.22	1.03 ± 0.23	1.03 ± 0.20	0.763
	Po	1.04 ± 0.23	1.03 ± 0.25	1.06 ± 0.19	0.274

Source: Study based on Furuyashiki et al., 2019.

By 2023, over 140 studies have been conducted on forest bathing worldwide, involving over 290 million people. Research has shown that staying in a green area, defined as an open, undeveloped space with natural vegetation, leads to significant health benefits (<https://spaeden.pl ›zdrowie-i-forma ›forma-i-ksztalt>; access: 25/08/2023). The healing power of nature cannot be underestimated - more and more people are turning to natural remedies, and nature is becoming a priceless resource that is under threat.

In the past, trees played an important role not only in medicine, but also in magic related to the mystery of life, fertility and death, and in religious worship. In many cultures, the tree was presented as a symbol of the entire universe, and in the mythologies of various peoples it had great importance. Each tree species emanates a different, special and characteristic energy. To reap the most positive benefits, choose healthy, most impressive trees with a thick trunk and plump leaves. Recently, natural methods of supporting the body in increasing immunity, coping with everyday stress, depression, neurosis have become more and more popular, and forest bathing has become a new trend. One of the most significant health benefits of forest bathing is its effect on the nervous system and its ability to reduce stress. Research has shown that staying in forest areas is associated with a reduction in cortisol levels, which is an indicator of the level of stress in the body (Twohig-Bennett, Jones, 2018). Additionally, studies conducted in Japan and China indicate that forest bathing may have benefits in terms

of lowering blood pressure, heart rate and improving overall mental well-being (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Differences in average heart rate during forest bathing and traditional walks around urban areas

Source: Study based on M. D. Li , 2016.

One common denominator of these methods is contact with nature, especially with the forest. This process is tree therapy, often referred to as sylvotherapy. It helps the body activate self-healing mechanisms, improves vitality, calms down and soothes by being surrounded by trees and bushes. If you want to recharge with positive energy, just hug the bark of a tree, e.g. birch, linden or oak. The importance of selected tree stands is presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Medicinal properties of selected stands

No.	Tree name	Healing properties
1.	Pine	It relieves stress, oxygenates the body and clears the mind. It is the largest producer of essential oils in the forest.
2.	Birch	It has a calming effect, relieves depression, strengthens, and supports the treatment of the urinary tract, liver, lungs and hyperthyroidism. It is the kindest tree in the world.
3.	Beech	It relieves stress and calms down. It helps you overcome shyness and regain self-confidence. It is recommended for people suffering from circulatory system, throat and kidney problems.
4.	Oak	Restores vitality, improves concentration, strengthens the psyche. It stimulates lymphatic vessels and blood circulation. A decoction of oak bark is used to treat skin diseases and reproductive organs.
5.	Linden tree	Minimizes fatigue, stimulates the respiratory and circulatory systems, restores balance. It soothes cough and runny nose and calms down. It is used for gargling and as a compress for wounds and ulcers.

6.	Maple	Helps establish open and honest relationships and gives courage. It is a symbol of happiness and success.
7.	Hornbeam	Removes the fear of aging and helps you believe in yourself. Increases the body's immunity. It helps with exhaustion and fatigue, calms cough, relieves hay fever, sinusitis and bronchitis.
8.	Ash tree	It helps us know and understand our feelings and emotions. It helps in spiritual development and improves mood. It gives you the desire to start new ventures or continue difficult responsibilities.
9.	Larch	Stimulates the will to live, enthusiasm and zest for action. It adds strength and facilitates their regeneration. It allows us to look deeper at everything that surrounds us, and thus arouses altruism.
10.	Horse chestnut	Relaxes muscles, cures insomnia and circulatory diseases, relieves anxiety and blues, clears the mind and improves well-being. It has a positive effect on the intimate sphere, the areas of speech, color and aesthetics, as well as the increase in vitality. It has antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties.

Source: Study based on M. Jalinik, Forest areas as a multi-faceted attraction tourist, Ed. Economics and Environment, Białystok 2021, pp. 64–73.

The beneficial effect of trees on the human body has been known for a long time (our ancestors were aware of the enormous potential of nature and strived to live in full harmony with it). In many cultures, various trees and shrubs have had a specific impact on people's health and well-being. Each of the selected stands has medicinal properties (Table 2). Trees are characterized by a very strong biofield, they symbolize vitality, life and rebirth. Their healing effects have already been scientifically confirmed, e.g. forest bathing. As numerous scientific studies show, direct contact with nature, and even the sight of it, has a positive impact on health. Spending free time surrounded by nature is a good habit - the benefits are invaluable.

Conclusions

The aim of the study was to present the importance of forest bathing as a form of sylvan tourism and their impact on the health of society.

Forest bathing has been scientifically proven to have multiple benefits for physical and mental health in recent years. Such practices, with roots in Japanese cultural traditions, have been recognized as an important tool in promoting health and well-being in many countries. The main aspects of forest bathing are:

- health benefits - forest bathing brings numerous benefits, including improving the functions of the immune system, respiratory system, sleep quality, as well as reducing stress and improving mental health (McEwan et al., 2023);
- forest bathing should benefit both tourists and the environment, promoting sustainable and multifunctional development and protection of forest ecosystems;
- although forest bathing has many benefits, there are also challenges, such as potential threats to forest ecosystems associated with intensive tourism. Therefore, appropriate environmental education and community involvement in sustainable development are recommended;
- some tree species, such as birch, linden, oak, pine and others, have a significant impact on human health;
- forest bathing is used not only in Japan, but also in European and Scandinavian countries, China, the United States and others.

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